

Adaptive hybrid particle swarm optimization and fuzzy logic controller for a solar-wind hybrid power system

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Feb 17, 2024

Revised Dec 18, 2024

Accepted Jan 19, 2025

Keywords:

DFIG

Fuzzy logic control

HPOPSO

Optimal torque

Optimum power point tracking

Solar wind hybrid power system

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the best modeling and control strategies for a grid-connected hybrid wind-solar power system to maximize energy production. For variable wind speeds, determine the optimal power point using fuzzy logic control, adopt an adaptive hill climb searching method, and compare it with an optimal torque control method for large inertia wind turbine (WT). The role of fuzzy logic controller (FLC) is to adjust the hill climbing search (HCS) technique's step-size according to the operating point. The doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) control system has two subsystems: rotor-side and grid-side converters. The active and reactive power have been indirectly regulated by adjusting the current on the d-q axis. The rotor side converter (RSC) controllers are responsible for controlling the WT's rotational speed to achieve the maximum power output. The grid side converter (GSC) manages the voltage at the DC link and keeps a unity power factor between the grid and GSC. Optimal hybrid power point tracking technique for use with photovoltaic systems in both constant and variable shade circumstances, based on particle swarm optimization (PSO) and perturb and observe (P&O). The optimal power point tracking (OPPT) approach is compared to three other methods: PSO, P&O, and hybrid P&O-PSO. The model has a total capacity of 2.249 MW, with wind capacity of 2 MW and solar capacity of 0.249 MW, and its efficiency is analyzed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Since the world's energy needs are growing, more renewable energy sources (RESs) are being used. This is to avoid the problems that come with fossil fuels, such as their high cost, quick depletion, and environment pollution. Nowadays, RESs have been deployed extensively due to their environmental friendliness and accessibility. Researchers anticipate producing pollution-free electricity with the use of RESs. Biomass, the sun, wind, and water are examples of naturally occurring, non-exhaustible, and non-polluting renewable sources of energy [1].

Optimization techniques for the design of a solar-wind hybrid power system (SWHPS) ensure electricity reliability while reducing system costs. SWHPS ensures a constant supply of electricity to end

consumers [2]. A hybrid system employs multiple energy sources, such as wind and solar photovoltaic (SPV), and is available with or without backup batteries [3]. The objective is to place greater emphasis on harnessing green energy resources in order to gradually decommission the traditional electrical grid, thereby reducing electric power bills.

Wind energy is anticipated to meet 20% of the world's energy needs by 2030 and is considered to be a viable source of energy. The collective wind power capacity reached 744 GW in 2020, covering more than 5% of worldwide electricity consumption [4]. The worldwide wind capacity reached 955 GW by the end of 2022. India's ability to make wind power has grown a lot in the last few years. As of January 31, 2023, the cumulative installed capacity of wind power was 42 GW, which made it the 4th largest installed capacity of wind power in the world [5].

The wind energy conversion system (WECS) has been enhanced over the past several decades to accommodate the rapid development of industrial wind technology. The wind turbine (WT) is the most important part of the WECS because it turns the kinetic energy of the wind into mechanical energy. On the global market, there are two different ways to set up WT. Compared to the variable speed wind turbine (VSWT), the fixed speed wind turbine (FSWT) is easy to build and has a small range of wind speeds. The VSWT has a number of advantages, including a high wind energy collection rate and a broad speed range with total controllability. Several generator types, including squirrel-cage induction generators (SCIGs), doubly-fed induction generators (DFIGs), and permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs), are utilized in variable-speed WECS [6].

Doubly fed induction generators (DFIGs) have gained significant popularity in the context of large-scale WECS. Consequently, extensive research has been conducted in recent years to investigate their operational and control aspects [7]. The operation of wind turbines is restricted to a predetermined range of wind velocities, which are delimited by cut-in and cut-out speeds. The WT must be halted beyond these boundaries to safeguard both the turbine and generator [8].

An optimum power point tracking (OPPT) algorithm must be incorporated into the system in order to determine the optimum working point of the WT. Many articles have been written about OPPT algorithms, such as power signal feedback (PSF) control, tip speed ratio (TSR) control, robust control, hill-climb searching (HCS) control, and optimal torque (OT) control [9], [10]. TSR control modulates the WT rotor speed to maintain an optimal TSR at which optimum power is extracted; nevertheless, this method has limitations due to the challenge of obtaining the optimum TSR and accurately measuring wind speed [11]. PSF and OT techniques need to know the optimum power curve (OPC) of the wind turbine. The control methods of the WT follows this curve. According to [12], it's hard to implement the model predictive control (MPC) accurately in practical implementations. The HCS method doesn't need data on wind speed or information on the turbine's attributes.

Numerous techniques have been investigated in the literature to enhance the HCS [13]. The adjustment mechanism for regulating the step size differs across various research groups, depending on the perturbed variable [14]. A few researchers used the converter's duty cycle as a control input to the system [15]. In some cases, the input voltage or the load current are applied as control inputs [16]. The research utilized the variation between the present speed of the generator (ω) and its optimum speed (ω^*) ascertained from the optimal power curve to systematically adjust the magnitude of perturbation at the completion of each cycle [17]. Studied many written wind OPPT approaches and decided that these two are the best because they can adapt to changing conditions and tune themselves [18].

The photovoltaic (PV) solar power generation is a technology that has been expanding rapidly in recent years. To offset the high initial cost, however, it is essential to maximize the use of solar PV technology [19]. This drives the development of high-efficiency, rapid-switching optimum power point tracking (OPPT) methods [20]. With the growing popularity of PV systems in major cities, it is becoming more challenging to find locations where partial shading conditions (PSC) do not occur for PV panel installations. Because of obstacles like buildings, towers, and trees, the solar irradiation received by PV modules is not evenly distributed [21]. This causes the power-voltage (P-V) curve to have multiple power peaks. The peaks in this curve are referred to as maximum power points (local optimum power point, or LOPP), and the peak with the highest power is referred to as the global optimum power point (GOPP) [22].

It has been found that conventional OPPT algorithms like perturbation and observation (P&O) and incremental conductance are unable to identify the distinction between local and global maximum points. Because of this, conventional approaches to OPP detection fail when partial shading is present [23]. Nonetheless, several studies utilizing OPPT strategies based on computational intelligence algorithms, such as fuzzy logic, evolutionary algorithms, particle swarm optimization, the shuffled frog hopping algorithm, and others, have been implemented to address this difficulty of the conventional techniques [24]. Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is one such technique that is both computationally simple and easy to implement; the major drawbacks of PSO are its lengthy tracking time and its wide search space [25].

In this paper, a SWHPS system consisting of a fuzzy logic controller-based adaptive HCS strategy is used as the OPPT technique, and it is compared to another OPPT strategy with better results, such as the OT control strategy. In order to attain optimal control of rotational speed response, simulation studies were carried out on a 2 MW DFIG to validate the study for wind systems. In addition, in PV systems, a hybrid approach was proposed, which has the benefit of speeding up the tracking process. The hybrid OPPT strategy that combines the P&O and PSO techniques for solar systems under constant and partial shade, this approach offers faster convergence than traditional PSO and reduced oscillations. More energy can be captured through this method compared to the alternatives.

2. SOLAR-WIND HYBRID POWER SYSTEM

A solar combined variable-speed wind energy system (SWHPS) is suggested in this proposed research work in which a DFIG is employed to convert wind energy to electrical energy and then integrated with an SPV system through the DC link of the converters, as illustrated in Figure 1. In SWHPS, the estimated capacity of both the solar and wind energy units is considered to be 2.249 MW. Rotor side converter (RSC) assists the wind energy system in operating at the optimal rotational speed specified by the wind OPPT technique. The grid side converter (GSC) regulates the frequency and voltage of the network.

Figure 1. Proposed solar-wind hybrid power system

The obtainable wind power (P_{obtain}) can be used to express the correlation between the input of mechanical power and the typical wind velocity of the turbine blades.

$$P_{obtain} = 0.5u^3A\rho \tag{1}$$

Where A represents the rotor swept area, ρ represents the density of the air, and u represents the wind speed. The expression for the power harnessed by the turbine is denoted as P_T , is a quotient of the total power that is obtainable, as represented by (2).

$$P_T = P_{obtain} \times C_p(\lambda \cdot \beta) \tag{2}$$

Where λ is the non-dimensional tip speed ratio, β is the pitch angle of the blade in radians, and $C_p(\lambda \cdot \beta)$ is the power capture coefficient.

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega_r R}{u} \tag{3}$$

Where R is the blade radius in meters and ω_r is the rotor speed in radians per second. T_{aerody} represent the aerodynamic torque exerted on the turbine rotor, the resulting power captured can be determined.

$$P_T = T_{aerody} \omega_r \quad (4)$$

The mathematical equation for T_{aerody} can be obtained by integrating (1), (2), and (4) and solving for it.

$$T_{aerody} = \gamma(u, \omega_r) C_P(\lambda, \beta) \quad (5)$$

Where, $\gamma = (1/2\omega_r) u^3 A \rho$ for $\omega_r > 0$. Using the TSR in (3), one can demonstrate that T_{aerody} is proportional to the ω_r^2 . The rotor shaft was mentioned in the motion equation for a connected generator and WT.

$$T_{aerody} - T_E = J \frac{d\omega_r}{dt} + G_D \omega_r \quad (6)$$

Where J is the corresponding total mass of the gearbox, rotor shaft, and blades; G_D is the gearbox's friction coefficient; and T_E is the generator's electrical torque.

2.1. dq0-reference frame DFIG model

If the stator and rotor parameters are changed into the rotating frame of reference, the mutual inductances between the stator-rotor exhibit independence with respect to both the speed of the high-speed rotor (ω_r), and position (θ_r). The $dq0$ conversion is utilized to change the abc quantities in the $dq0$ reference frame with an angle disparity between the frames [26]. Applying Kirchhoff's voltage law (KVL) for the stator windings and the Park translation, stator winding differential equations are as (7) and (8).

$$V_{sq} = -R_s i_{sq} + \frac{d\lambda_{sq}}{dt} - \omega \lambda_{sd} \quad (7)$$

$$V_{sd} = -R_s i_{sd} + \frac{d\lambda_{sd}}{dt} - \omega \lambda_{sq} \quad (8)$$

Where R_s represents resistance/phase of the stator winding and ω represents the frame's angular velocity. These equations are depicted as block diagrams in Figure 2. Similar computational procedures can be applied to the rotor circuits by substituting $(\theta - \theta_r)$ for the term in the $dq0$ conversion for rotor quantities.

$$V_{rq} = R_r i_{rq} + \frac{d\lambda_{rq}}{dt} + (\omega - \omega_r) \lambda_{rd} \quad (9)$$

$$V_{rd} = -R_r i_{rd} + \frac{d\lambda_{rd}}{dt} - (\omega - \omega_r) \lambda_{rq} \quad (10)$$

Additionally, the stator-flux coupling formulae can also be translated to the $dq0$ frame of reference as (11) and (12).

$$\lambda_{sq} = -L_s i_{sq} + L_m i_{rq} \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda_{sd} = -L_s i_{sd} + L_m i_{rd} \quad (12)$$

Where L_s and L_m indicates stator-self and mutual-inductance. Similarly, the rotor flux coupling equations can be transformed to the $dq0$ reference frame as (13) and (14).

$$\lambda_{rq} = L_r i_{rq} - L_m i_{sq} \quad (13)$$

$$\lambda_{rd} = L_r i_{rd} - L_m i_{sd} \quad (14)$$

Where L_r is self-inductance of the rotor. Finally, the derived DFIG electromagnetic torque is given as (15).

$$T_E = 0.75 * P (i_{sq} \lambda_{sd} - i_{sd} \lambda_{sq}) \quad (15)$$

Where P is the pole count. The (7) through (15) are all that are required to design a DFIG in this study. The grid detects the stator voltages, V_{sd} and V_{sq} , and the rotor currents, i_{sd} and i_{sq} , are regulated by the rotor-side converter; consequently, λ_{sq} and λ_{sd} are acquired as depicted in Figure 2. Other variables can be determined using mathematical equation, such as i_{sd} , i_{sq} , from (9) and (10) (ignoring $\frac{d\lambda_{rq}}{dt}$ and $\frac{d\lambda_{rd}}{dt}$) and T_E from (15).

Power converters exhibit significantly quicker dynamics compared to generators and windmills. Consequently, in order to investigate slow dynamic occurrences, it is possible to design the rotor and grid-side converters using their respective controls and 1st-order transfer functions, as depicted in Figure 3. In the RSC, i_{rd} is fixed at zero, and i_{rq} is controlled by the required electrical torque, T_E^* . The GSC should estimate both the power and the DC-link voltage. Nevertheless, the power of the GSC can be estimated as (16).

$$P_i = 1.5(i_{iq}V_{iq} - i_{id}V_{id}) \tag{16}$$

Where V_{id} and V_{iq} denote the direct and quadrature inverter voltages, correspondingly, and are derived from V_{sd} and V_{sq} , as can be observed. The GSC-links the grid and the stator with a modified low-pass filter represented by an RL circuit. The $dq0$ transformation and KVL equations are used to derive V_{id} and V_{iq} , respectively.

$$V_{id} = V_{sd} - R_f i_{id} - L_f \frac{di_{id}}{dt} + L_f \omega i_{iq} \tag{17}$$

$$V_{iq} = V_{sq} - R_f i_{iq} - L_f \frac{di_{iq}}{dt} - L_f \omega i_{id} \tag{18}$$

V_{sd} and V_{sq} are derived from an equivalent set of mathematical equations for the power line, considering the known grid voltage. Utilizing Kirchhoff's current law (KCL) and ignoring the conduction loss of the converters, the voltage on the DC-bus is determined as (19).

$$\frac{0.5 d(V_{DC}^2)}{c dt} = P_r - P_i \tag{19}$$

C represents capacitor on the DC-bus, P_i and P_r represents grid and rotor side converter power. Back-to-back converters have their i_{rq} values determined by the electrical torque they need to generate, whereas rotor-side converters have their i_{iq} values determined by the DC-bus voltage they need to generate their required active power in the GSC. Each of these converter designs is depicted in Figures 3(a) and 3(b).

Figure 2. Computations of stator flux, λ_{sd} and λ_{sq} , based on the given input signals i_{rd} , i_{rq} , V_{sq} , and V_{sd}

Figure 3. Converter controller: (a) RSC, i_{rq} controlled according to the required T_e^* and (b) GSC, i_{iq} controlled according to the required V_{DC}^*

3. OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM FOR SOLAR-WIND HYBRID POWER SYSTEM

This investigation will use the determined speed of rotation as input and the obtained power as output for the system. To determine the appropriate perturbation size, one can rely on fuzzy logic controller (FLC), the variation in speed and mechanical power are used as input parameters ($\partial\omega_M$ and ∂P_M), and the change in reference speed is the output ($\partial\omega_M^*$). Figure 4 depicts fuzzy controller membership functions. Triangular uniform membership functions are a viable option for both input and output, as they offer higher sensitivity, particularly when parameters reach zero [27]. The FLC operates on the basis of perturbing the speed of reference and observing the ensuing variation in power. If there was an increase in output power alongside the most recent speed rise, the search would go in the same direction. Conversely, if increasing the speed results in a decrease in power output, the search direction will be reversed [28], [29].

Table 1 presents the rule table that corresponds to the fuzzy-HCS (FHCS) controller. The FHCS is an effective technique for tracking the optimum power point, particularly when wind conditions are frequently changing. Figure 5 depicts the schematic diagram of the OPPT control. Taking into consideration the power losses in the drivetrain and assuming the converters are lossless, the mechanical power can be calculated using (20).

$$P_{M_esti} = P_r + P_s + P_{LOSS_DT} = (1 - g)P_s + P_{LOSS_DT} \tag{20}$$

$$T_{HSS_OPT} = 0.5R^5\pi\rho \frac{C_{P_MAX}}{\lambda_{OPT}^3} \omega_m^2 = K_{OPT}\omega_m^2 \tag{21}$$

The technique employed depends on torque control, whereby the optimal torque curve is expressed mathematically as (21) and used as a reference torque for the controller that is linked to the WT. The frictional loss in torque is so negligible that it is ignored by our control system as well. Figure 6 depicts a detailed schematic of the OT control. Figure 7 depicts the suggested H-OPPT algorithm's flowchart. The algorithm keeps the operating point at the OPP through P&O until it detects partial shade [30], [31].

In the "OP-track sub-program," the suitable voltage range is selected. This region is scanned by the PSO, which returns the highest Pi value. The importance of tracking future peaks is examined. If the power disparity condition is met, the value of the GOPP is calculated by contrasting each of the recorded OPP power values. If the criterion fails, the similar operation is continued till all peaks are considered. When the "OP-track sub-program" returns, the P&O technique continues to keep the operating point at the OPPT [32], [33].

The SPV system is associated to the back-to-back (BTB) which converter the DC-link. Since the DC power produced can be supplied into the grid, no additional inverter is required. MATLAB/Simulink are used to simulate a stand-alone SPV system with various OPPT techniques. To select the best OPPT method for a stand-alone SPV scheme, Simulink modeling of the scheme is developed and connected to the boost converter.

Table 1. Presents the rule table that corresponds to the fuzzy-HCS (FHCS) controller

$\partial\omega_m$	∂P_m								
	NVB	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB	PVB
N	PVB	PB	PM	PS	Z	NS	NM	NB	NVB
Z	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PM	PB	PB
P	NVB	NB	NM	NS	Z	PM	PM	PB	PVB

Figure 4. Depicts fuzzy controller membership functions: (a) input ω_M , (b) input ∂P_M , and (c) output membership

Figure 5. Depicts a detailed schematic of the OPPT control

Figure 6. Depicts a detailed schematic of the OT control

Figure 7. Flowcharts for the suggested hybrid PSO-P&O MPPT method: (a) main-program and (b) OP-track sub-program

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The suggested SWHPS design is modeled utilizing the MATLAB/Simulink platform, including the PV, WT, BTB converter, DFIG device, transformer, and grid filter. The DFIG device is linked to the grid through the stator. The rotor is linked to the grid through a BTB converter and transformer.

4.1. Validation of Solar PV OPPT for SWHPS

The module utilized for simulation is an array type: Trina Solar TSM-250PA05.38, 10 series modules, 100 parallel strings. Table 2 contains the detailed specifications for the solar module. The hybrid PSO-P&O, PSO, and P&O OPPT approaches have been applied to this system, and the efficiencies of all three have been compared.

Table 3 shows an overview of the evaluation results for the MPPT methods performed in the first and second cases. For the first case, which simulates constant shading conditions, it is evident that all the algorithms effectively track the GOPP. This demonstrates that the HPOPSO technique presented in this work is capable of extracting more power under a constant regime with no changes to environmental circumstances.

In the second case, a time interval in which a variation in shading circumstances occurs is evaluated. It begins with uniform shade conditions, with solar irradiance of $1000 \frac{W}{m^2}$, and after some time, the solar irradiance reduces to $800 \frac{W}{m^2}$, $600 \frac{W}{m^2}$, $400 \frac{W}{m^2}$, and $200 \frac{W}{m^2}$ in PV modules at $t = 0 s$, $t = 2 s$, $t = 3 s$, and $t = 4 s$, indicating the transition from uniform to partial shading. Comparing the suggested method to traditional PSO and P&O, it is evident that the suggested method has a faster convergence rate, thereby lowering the tracking time. It has the benefit of steadiness under the permanent regime, which translates to a greater power output as shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Table 2. Solar module parameters for simulation of SPV, OPPT, and SWHPS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Maximum power (P_{MAX})	249.85 W	Open circuit voltage (V_{OC})	37.6 V
Maximum current (I_{MAX})	8.06 A	Series modules	10
Short circuit current (I_{SC})	8.55 A	Parallel strings	100
Maximum voltage (V_{MAX})	31 V		

Table 3. The effectiveness of the OPPT techniques in the different irradiation conditions

Parameter		Proposed HPOPSO	P&O	PSO
First case-constant shading condition	Maximum power (W)	2.472×10^5	2.370×10^5	1.848×10^5
	Mean power (W)	2.055×10^5	1.889×10^5	1.699×10^5
	Maximum voltage (V)	2723	2722	2354
	Mean voltage (V)	2419	2370	2235
Second case-partial shading condition	Maximum power (W)	2.315×10^5	2.101×10^5	2.267×10^5
	Mean power (W)	9.926×10^4	9.643×10^4	9.142×10^4
	Maximum voltage (V)	2635	2608	2317
	Mean voltage (V)	1627	1587	1617

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Case 1-hybrid PSO-P&O, PSO: (a) output power vs. time and (b) output voltage vs. time

Figure 9. Case 2-hybrid PSO-P&O, PSO: (a) output power vs. time and (b) output voltage vs. time

4.2. Validation of DFIG-WT MPPT

A study was conducted on a 2 MW DFIG system with the suggested adaptive fuzzy-HCS (FHCS) controller. The DFIG specifications are listed in Table 4. The aim of the simulation is to implement a stepped-wind speed in an abrupt manner with the purpose of emulating potent wind turbulence. The suggested FHCS technique should provide the optimum rotating speed for the system and compete with the OT control technique with regard to effectiveness and response speed.

Figure 10(a) (see Appendix) displays a wind speed that includes a range of variable speeds, spanning from the cut-in to the rated wind speeds. Figure 10(b) (see Appendix) displays the change in rotational speed and its corresponding conceptual optimum speed, which vary in accordance with variations in wind speed. The FHCS technique seems to be faster and more stable, even when the wind speed changes, compared to the OT control. Figure 10(c) (see Appendix) shows the DFIG's output power, the WT's rated power, and the theoretical optimum mechanical power. The FHCS control technique seems more stable, while the OT has problems with oscillations. Regarding efficiency, both OPPT techniques yield almost identical average amounts of power, particularly at medium wind speeds.

Figure 10(d) (see Appendix) displays the electrical torque and the associated mechanical torque for each OPPT technique. The dynamics of both of these torques highlight the distinction between the two OPPT techniques. The OT control technique is more stable and slower as it employs the calculated optimum torque and utilizes the slow dynamic of the speed of rotation, this dynamic is dependent on the WT's inertia. Whereas, the FHCS technique employs a closed-loop speed control system that adjusts the speed of reference based on the distance between the optimum and actual operational points. The huge fluctuations observed in the FHCS technique provide evidence of its superior dynamic response. Figures 10(e) and 10(f) (see Appendix) display the rotor and stator currents generated through the OT and FHCS power optimization techniques; they vary based on the magnitude of the output power, while the frequency of the rotor current varies based on the rotating speed, whereas the frequency of the stator currents is kept at the same level as the grid frequency. Furthermore, it is evident that the FHCS control technique is greater stable compared to the OT technique.

Figure 10(g) (see Appendix) displays the C_p response. In terms of speed, both techniques appear to be nearly equal. However, the FHCS technique outperforms in sustaining the optimal value of C_p regardless of wind speed changes. However, the OT faces an issue with the step-size seeking process while in steady-state operation. The time required for this procedure depends on the mechanical features of the WT. Nevertheless, the variance between them, which is 0.51–0.49, can be considered acceptable.) displays the TSR attributes, which accomplish the optimum level and maintain it across both OPPT techniques. Figure 10(h) (see Appendix) illustrates the pitch angle changes based on the system's operating point, ranging from 0 to 3.3 s. During this time, the pitch orientation system operates to restrict the power and speed to the rated points. However, after this period, the pitch orientation system is disengaged to enable the OPPT system to function without any restrictions. According to simulation findings and evaluation, the FHCS technique was found to be the most stable and effective because it keeps looking for the best operating point without needing to know any information regarding the wind speed or WT characteristics. The OT technique is fast but less effective at maintaining steady state, but its dependence on WT characteristics rendered it inflexible.

Table 4. DFIG parameters for the simulation of WT-MPPT and SWHPS

Parameters	Value
Rated power (P_{RATED})	2.0 MW
Rated torque (T_{RATED})	12734 Nm
Stator current (I_S)	1.980 kA
Working frequency	50 Hz
Switching frequency	4 KHz
Rated rotor voltage	2.072 kV
DC bus voltage	1.154 kV
Stator voltage (V_{STAOR})	0.692 kV
No of pole pairs	2
Speed of the rotor shaft	1500 rpm
L_M	2.6 mH
R_R	2.90 mΩ
R_S	2.8 mΩ
Σ	0.088 mH

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines and discusses an adaptive OPPT algorithm for DFIG-equipped WT systems and solar PV systems. The result of simulations on a standalone SPV scheme using hybrid PSO-P&O evidently presented the technique as more efficient than PSO and P&O OPPT techniques. The suggested hybrid algorithm was able to successfully follow OPP in both constant and varying shade scenarios, with tracking times that were 50% faster than those achieved using the traditional PSO and P&O techniques. Also, the proposed technology can increase the amount of energy made by the PV system by 0.3%. Also, this research examined a simulation and made a comparison between the suggested technique and the traditional OT control technique with respect to efficiency and response time. Simulations showed that the OT and fuzzy-HCS control methods were almost as accurate as each other. The OT technique is also quick response, flexible, and efficient, but it can be hard to figure out what the best step size is, which can lead to more fluctuating results. Nevertheless, its inflexibility was attributed to its reliance on the specific characteristics of wind turbines. The fuzzy-HCS methodology achieved the highest mean C_p value and exhibited superior capacity for maintaining this maximum value, even when subjected to variations in wind velocity, as compared to the OT approach. By choosing the appropriate adaptive step-size techniques, it is possible to enhance performance and address the issues in the suggested technique.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The authors declare that no financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [GBAK], upon reasonable request.

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APPENDIX

Figure 10. Shows the dynamic responses of the FHSC technique in different speed modes: (a) wind speed, (b) rotational speed, (c) output power, and (d) torque

Figure 10. Shows the dynamic responses of the FHSC technique in different speed modes: (e) rotor current, (f) stator current, (g) efficiency coefficient, and (h) pitch angle (continued)

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